

A phase I/II randomised controlled clinical trial to assess the feasibility, safety and preliminary effectiveness of paracetamol in resolving acute kidney injury in children with severe malaria.

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Abstract

Background:

Acute kidney injury (AKI) is prevalent among children with severe malaria, contributing to considerable morbidity and mortality. Oxidative stress has been implicated in the pathophysiology of malaria-induced AKI, and paracetamol, with its antioxidant properties, has been proposed as a solution. Therefore, we conducted the first study in children to assess the feasibility, safety and preliminary effectiveness of paracetamol in ameliorating AKI in severe malaria.

Methods:

We conducted a phase I/II open label parallel randomised controlled trial of 40 hospitalised children aged >6month to <12 years with malaria-induced AKI in eastern Uganda. Participants were randomized by a sealed envelope 1:1 to receive either oral paracetamol 20mg/kg 6-hourly for 48 hours or tepid sponging every 30 minutes until fever subsided. Only the assessors of the primary outcome were masked to the intervention. The primary outcome was renal recovery at 48 hours assessed using restricted mean survival time (RMST) in intention to treat population of children according to their randomisation groups.

Results:

Between 19 September 2021 and 25 August 2023, 250 children with haemoglobinuric severe malaria were screened and the 40 enrolled were randomly assigned paracetamol (n=20) or tepid sponging (n=20). The mean age was 6.54 (2.61) years. The mean time to renal recovery in the paracetamol group was 0.491 hours (95% CI: -9.265 to 10.248; p=0.921) longer than the no paracetamol group within 48 hours, but this difference was not statistically significant even after adjusting for age and weight: 1.04 hours (95% CI: -8.61, 10.70; p=0.832). The safety assessment indicated no significant differences in adverse events and hepatotoxicity in either group.

Conclusions:

Although Paracetamol was safe, it did not significantly improve renal recovery in children with malaria-induced AKI. Further larger studies are needed to explore this role of paracetamol.

The trial registration: ISRCTN84974248.

Background

Malaria remains a significant cause of childhood morbidity and mortality in sub-Saharan Africa (SSA). In 2023, the region recorded 246 million cases and 569,000 deaths constituting over 94% and 95% of the global cases and deaths, respectively [1]. Notably, children under five years, are disproportionately affected by this burden [2-4]. AKI is a prevalent severe malaria presentation with reports indicating incidence rates of up to 46% among paediatric patients [2, 5-7]. Furthermore, children with malaria-induced AKI are at an increased risk of mortality [4, 6, 8, 9], often requiring renal replacement therapy, such as dialysis [10]. However, in low-resource settings, these interventions are often inaccessible,

necessitating the reliance on supportive care measures, such as fluid therapy [11]. While essential, caution should be exercised when giving supportive care, as fluid boluses previously recommended have been shown to increase mortality in some cases [12]. These challenges further compound this burden with up to 12% of the survivors developing [13].

Recent studies have indicated that paracetamol, a widely used antipyretic and analgesic agent, has shown potential as a renoprotective agent in the management of AKI. Preclinical studies suggest it mitigates oxidative stress and inflammation, two key drivers of AKI in severe malaria. It does this by counteracting cell-free haemoglobin (CFHb)-induced lipid peroxidation by converting ferryl haem to the less harmful Fe³⁺ state and neutralises globin radicals [14, 15]. In addition, it has been observed to reduce endothelial activation and microvascular dysfunction by inhibiting NADPH oxidase (NOX) activity, which may prevent CFHb-induced release of von Willebrand factor (vWF), P-selectin, and angiopoietin-2 (Ang-2) from endothelial cells [16, 17]. Early clinical studies support these findings, linking paracetamol to reductions in renal injury markers, such as serum creatinine, and improved renal function in adults with sepsis [18-20]. Furthermore, a randomised trial in Bangladeshi adults with moderate and severe malaria showed paracetamol's ability to improve kidney function and lower AKI risk, particularly among patients with elevated CFHb [21].

While these findings are promising, our understanding of the renoprotective effects of paracetamol in the paediatric population, particularly in children with malaria-induced AKI, remains limited. The extant literature has predominantly focused on adult cohorts with sepsis [18-20], resulting in a critical gap regarding safety, optimal dosing and efficacy of paracetamol for this use case in children. Moreover, paracetamol has been observed to induce hepatotoxicity in children, who under these circumstances are already at risk of liver dysfunction due to severe malaria [22]. To address these gaps, we conducted the first phase I/II randomised controlled trial in children to assess the feasibility, safety and preliminary effectiveness of paracetamol in ameliorating AKI among children with severe malaria.

Methods

Study setting

The trial was conducted at Mbale Regional Referral Hospital (MRRH), a tertiary hospital in eastern Uganda, a region endemic for malaria. The hospital serves as a referral centre for paediatric cases in the region.

Study design

We conducted a phase I/II open-label, randomised controlled trial that utilised a parallel design with a 1:1 allocation ratio.

Study Population

Eligibility criteria

Inclusion criteria

- Children aged >6month and <12 years
- Positive blood smear for *P. falciparum* malaria at admission
- Haemoglobinuria with any of these; impaired consciousness and/or severe respiratory distress, severe Anaemia (Hb <5g/dl), prostration
- Serum creatinine increase by $\geq 0.3\text{mg/dL}$ within 48hours or to ≥ 1.5 times baseline.
- Elevated BUN >20mg/dL
- Guardian or parent willing and able to provide consent

Exclusion criteria

- Acute trauma or burns
- Known allergy to paracetamol
- Impaired liver function tests /disease with ALT beyond 40IU/l
- Treated with Paracetamol in the last 24 hours prior to admission
- Known chronic renal failure
- Known malignancy
- Vomiting everything
- Refusal to consent
- Previously enrolled

Study Interventions

Intervention arm

Participants in the intervention arm received paracetamol 20mg/kg administered orally 6-hourly for 48h plus standard of care for severe malaria. Patients unable to swallow received paracetamol by nasogastric tube. In case the patient vomited within 30 min of paracetamol administration, a further dose was given.

Control arm

Participants in the control arm received tepid sponging and fanning every 30 minutes plus standard of care for severe malaria. After every 30 minutes, the axillary temperature was taken and in case it exceeded 39.5°C, a rescue treatment (paracetamol 10mg/kg as per treatment guidelines for fever) was given.

Outcomes

Primary outcome

The primary outcome for this trial was renal recovery time at 48hr defined using normalisation of two renal biomarkers: serum creatinine (Cr) levels <80 µmol/L and Blood urea nitrogen (BUN) levels <20mg/dL. Both renal biomarkers were required to normalise to define renal recovery at 48 hours, providing a stringent and clinically meaningful measure of kidney function improvement by capturing both glomerular filtration and nitrogen excretion. The threshold cut offs used were based on internationally accepted criteria for the resolution of paediatric AKI.

Secondary outcomes

Secondary outcomes of this trial included:

Renal recovery at day 28 defined as sustained normalisation of serum creatinine and BUN levels at day 28.

Safety outcomes included assessment of adverse events and monitoring for hepatotoxicity. Monitoring of hepatotoxicity using Hy's law: Safety monitoring in this trial included assessment of liver function tests (LFTs) to identify potential hepatotoxicity associated with paracetamol. Hy's law criteria were used as follows: Alanine transaminase (ALT) or aspartate transaminase (AST) levels >3x the upper limit of normal (ULN), total bilirubin >2X ULN in the absence of significant cholestasis (elevated alkaline phosphatase) and no other plausible explanation for observed liver injury.

Mortality: Mortality at 48 hours and day 28 were recorded to assess the overall safety and survival effect of the intervention.

Sample size

Using the A'Hern table of sample size determination, (with the assumption of $P_0 = 10\%$ $P_1 = 25\%$ $\alpha = 0.05$ $\beta = 0.1$ $d = 0.1$), we arrived at the sample size $n = 40$ with an estimated response rate $r = 0.1$. While the sample size was small and limited statistical power, it was consistent with phase I/II trials designed to evaluate treatment feasibility and safety rather than definitive efficacy.

Procedure

The PARIST study protocol was published and gives a detailed description of the various study procedures [23].

Screening

Eligible participants were identified by trained nurses and clinicians and registered in the eligibility screening log. A study team member performed a rapid structured assessment; of conscious level, vital signs (heart rate, oxygen saturation, respiratory rate, axillary temperature, and blood pressure) and history of haemoglobinuria in the current illness defined by dark urine with Hillmen urine colour chart grade >5 (see figure1 supplementary material). Children who were potentially eligible had a rapid test using iSTAT® to determine creatinine levels and or BUN levels. Details of those fulfilling the entry criteria were entered onto a screening form, while reasons for non-eligibility were added to the eligibility screening log.

Randomization and masking

After screening, the patients who qualified were assigned study numbers which correspond to those assigned in envelopes which were arranged consecutively in sealed opaque envelopes, each assigned across the seal. These numbers were randomly assigned prior to the start of the study by an independent statistician using the "randomizeR" package of the statistical software R, which allows simple randomization and adaptive assignment through a minimization procedure. Minimization allocated patients to best maintain balance in the treatment group by calculating an imbalance score at each randomization. It then assigned with higher probability each patient to the treatment that would reduce the imbalance. The allocation was on a 1:1 ratio to Paracetamol (A) and No Paracetamol (B). During enrolment, the study staff picked the cards consecutively and opened it. Each envelope had a card that showed which arm the participant was in (A or B). Due to the nature of the intervention, neither participants nor staff were blinded to allocation but were sturdily instructed not to disclose the allocation status of the participant at the follow-up assessments. Although the trial was open-label, blinding was maintained for outcome assessors and statisticians to minimise bias in the outcome measurement and analysis of results.

Delivery of the intervention

The intervention was initiated as soon as possible following randomization. The study investigational product. Paracetamol tablets 500mg (Kamadol, Kampala Pharmaceutical Industries (KPI) Limited)) was sourced locally from a certified pharmaceutical supplier and stored according to the manufacturer's recommendations. Treatment protocols and guidelines for paracetamol administration and monitoring were provided to the trial clinical team. The intervention was administered by trained clinicians and

nurses. All the staff involved in the trial received prior training on the study protocol, including paracetamol administration, safety monitoring and adverse event reporting. Clinical staff were trained to follow strict procedures to ensure correct dosing and adherence to the study protocol. Every staff member qualification and training were captured in the trial 's personnel log.

Laboratory investigations

Following consent and randomisation, admission blood samples were taken for the following investigations: lactate, glucose and malaria status. In accordance with national guidelines, HIV testing was done after admission procedures were complete and consent was given by parents or guardians. Haemoglobin and lactate were reassessed at 8hr (post-resuscitation), 12 hours, 24 hours and 48 hours. An additional blood test (2-3mls) was taken at the 28-day follow-up to check haematological and parasitological recovery.

Clinical Monitoring and further assessments

All children were reassessed clinically at 1, 4, 8, 24 and 48 hours. At each review consciousness level, urine output and fluid intake, daily body weight measurement, vital signs (heart rate, oxygen saturation, respiratory rate, axillary temperature, blood pressure). Creatinine and BUN were measured at 0, 12, 24 hours and thereafter daily till 5 days of admission or until normal. In addition, serum electrolytes assessment was monitored. Participants were subsequently followed up on day 28, 90 and 180 to assess secondary outcomes. All medications and supportive care were administered under the supervision of trained clinical staff to ensure adherence to the study protocol.

Safety monitoring

Safety monitoring was an integral component of this trial to ensure participant well-being. The adverse events and severe adverse events were monitored continuously during the study period, including emesis, right upper quadrant pain, tachycardia, hypoglycaemia, hypotension and impaired liver function documenting and categorising them based on the Common Terminology Criteria for Adverse Events (CTCAE), and timely reporting them to the principal investigator. An independent DSMB oversaw the trial, conducting regular periodic reviews to ensure participant safety and the scientific integrity of the study.

Data management

All clinical and laboratory data was recorded using a standardised case report form (CRF) by a trained study team. Data was entered into a secure, password-protected Redcap database at the Mbale Clinical Research Institute (MCRI), with routine audits for completeness and accuracy. Consistency checks were conducted to resolve any discrepancies. Participant confidentiality was secured by de-identifying

records, and access to the database was restricted to authorised study staff. Furthermore, all data was anonymised before the presentation or publication of any results.

Statistical analysis

All trial analyses were conducted on an intention-to-treat (ITT) basis, including all randomised participants in their allocated groups and the level of statistical significance set at $p < 0.05$. The primary outcome (renal recovery at 48 hours) was analysed using the restricted mean survival time (RMST) approach. Although traditional survival analysis methods were prespecified for analysis of survival outcomes, these methods were not used due to the violation of the proportional hazard's assumption. In particular, the Shoenfelds residual test (supplementary figure 2) showed that the hazard ratio for treatment was not constant over time. Consequently we adopted the restricted mean survival time (RMST) approach, which estimates the mean survival time within a restricted time window allowing for the direct comparison between groups without the limitations imposed by the proportional hazards assumption [24]. The cumulative recovery time was compared between the paracetamol and control arms at a truncation time ($\tau = 48$ hours) and results were reported as differences in the RMST together with the 95% confidence interval. RMST was also used to compare renal recovery between the two arms at day 28 ($\tau = 672$ hours). Adjusted RMST analyses were performed to control for potential confounding effects of baseline covariates including age and weight in both the primary and secondary outcome analyses. Age was selected because renal function and recovery may vary with developmental stage [25] while the selection of weight was to account for differences in the distribution and dosing, which may influence treatment efficacy [26]. These models provided adjusted estimates of group differences in renal recovery time. Secondary outcomes including the frequency of participants with adverse events and those meeting the Hy's law criteria for hepatotoxicity were compared between the two arms using Fisher's exact test. Further descriptive statistics were used to summarise changes in LFTs over the time points of assessment for each of the groups. Owing to the small sample size, no subgroup analysis was done. All statistical analyses were performed using R statistical software (version 4.3.2).

Trial registration

PARIST study was registered with the International Standard Randomised Controlled Trial Number (ISRCTN) registry under the identifier ISRCTN 84974248.

Results

Participant Characteristics and Study Flow

A total of 250 children diagnosed with haemoglobinuric severe malaria were initially screened for eligibility into the study. Following this screening process, a random sample of 40 participant were selected using a predefined inclusion and exclusion criteria, and these 40 participants were then

randomly allocated into two groups on a 1:1 ratio: the intervention group (n = 20), which received oral paracetamol 20mg/kg every 6 hourly for 48 hour plus standard of care for severe malaria and the control group (n = 20), which received tepid sponging and fanning every 30 minutes plus with the standard of care for severe malaria. The screening and randomisation process were carried out in strict accordance with the trial protocol. All participants who were randomised completed the primary outcome assessment at 48 hours with minimal loss to follow-up (3/40) during the subsequent post discharge evaluations. This trial was conducted between 19 September 2021 and 25 August 2023. The CONSORT diagram (Fig. 1) provides a summary of the study participant's flow.

Baseline Characteristics

The baseline characteristics including demographic, clinical, and laboratory characteristic of study participants were comparable between the paracetamol and control group (Table 1). For instance, the mean age of participants was 7.3 ± 2.4 years in the paracetamol group and 6.9 ± 2.5 years in the control group. Male participants comprised 55% and 50% of the paracetamol and control groups, respectively. Baseline serum creatinine levels were 1.6 ± 0.3 mg/dL in the paracetamol group and 1.7 ± 0.4 mg/dL in the control group, while blood urea nitrogen (BUN) levels were 26.1 ± 5.2 mg/dL and 25.9 ± 6.0 mg/dL, respectively.

Table 1
Baseline demographic, clinical, and laboratory characteristics of study participants in the two intervention groups.

Characteristic	Overall, N = 40 ¹	No Paracetamol, N = 20 ¹	Paracetamol, N = 20 ¹
Sex			
Female	17 (41%)	8 (40%)	9 (42%)
Male	23 (59%)	12 (60%)	11 (58%)
Age	6.54 (2.61)	6.66 (2.82)	6.43 (2.44)
Axillary Temperature (°C)	37.03 (0.75)	37.15 (0.88)	36.90 (0.58)
Weight (Kg)	18.3 (3.6)	18.5 (3.9)	18.1 (3.4)
Lactate	2.07 (1.36)	1.98 (1.34)	2.15 (1.42)
Yellow eyes			
Yes	40 (100%)	20 (100%)	19 (100%)
Capillary refill (sec)			
< 2 sec	21 (54%)	11 (55%)	10 (53%)
2–3 sec	18 (46%)	9 (45%)	9 (47%)
Temperature gradient	1 (2.6%)	1 (5.0%)	0 (0%)
Pallor			
Mild	2 (5.1%)	2 (10%)	0 (0%)
Moderate	14 (36%)	4 (20%)	10 (53%)
Severe	23 (59%)	14 (70%)	9 (47%)
Sunken eyes	2 (5.1%)	1 (5.0%)	1 (5.3%)
Dry mucus	6 (15%)	4 (20%)	2 (11%)
Level of consciousness			
Alert	37 (95%)	18 (90%)	19 (100%)
Verbal	2 (5.1%)	2 (10%)	0 (0%)
Prostration	19 (49%)	11 (55%)	8 (42%)
Jaundice			
Mild	20 (51%)	11 (55%)	9 (47%)

Characteristic	Overall, N = 40 ¹	No Paracetamol, N = 20 ¹	Paracetamol, N = 20 ¹
Moderate	17 (44%)	9 (45%)	8 (42%)
Severe	2 (5.1%)	0 (0%)	2 (11%)
Na ⁺ (mmol/L)	134.9 (3.5)	134.8 (3.0)	135.1 (4.2)
K ⁺ (mmol/L)	4.25 (0.71)	4.36 (0.67)	4.13 (0.75)
Cl ⁻ (mmol/L)	102.6 (5.2)	102.3 (6.0)	102.9 (4.2)
iCa (mmol/L)	1.10 (0.09)	1.10 (0.08)	1.10 (0.10)
TCO (mmol/L)	18.73 (3.03)	18.65 (3.27)	18.82 (2.83)
Glucose (mmol/L)	27 (116)	44 (155)	6 (2)
BUN (mg/dL)	69 (44)	66 (43)	73 (47)
Creatinine (mg/dL)	2.42 (3.04)	2.63 (3.51)	2.18 (2.50)
Anion Gap (mmol/L)	18.95 (2.34)	19.25 (2.65)	18.59 (1.94)
WBC (10 ³ /uL)	11 (8)	12 (7)	10 (9)
NEU (%)	63 (20)	66 (18)	59 (23)
Hb (g/dL)	5.91 (1.99)	5.58 (2.33)	6.25 (1.56)
PLT (10 ³ /uL)	198 (156)	202 (153)	194 (163)
Dark urine grade (Hillmen urine colour chart number (1–10))			
5	7 (20%)	4 (24%)	3 (17%)
6	8 (23%)	4 (24%)	4 (22%)
7	14 (40%)	5 (29%)	9 (50%)
8	2 (5.7%)	2 (12%)	0 (0%)
9	2 (5.7%)	1 (5.9%)	1 (5.6%)
10	2 (5.7%)	1 (5.9%)	1 (5.6%)
Urine bilirubin			
Moderate ++	1 (3.1%)	0 (0%)	1 (6.3%)
Negative	27 (84%)	15 (94%)	12 (75%)

Characteristic	Overall, N = 40 ¹	No Paracetamol, N = 20 ¹	Paracetamol, N = 20 ¹
Small +	4 (13%)	1 (6.3%)	3 (19%)
Urine ketone (mg/dL)			
Moderate	1 (3.1%)	0 (0%)	1 (6.3%)
Negative	24 (75%)	10 (63%)	14 (88%)
Small	3 (9.4%)	3 (19%)	0 (0%)
Trace	4 (13%)	3 (19%)	1 (6.3%)
Urine blood (non-haemolyzed)			
Negative	5 (83%)	4 (100%)	1 (50%)
Trace	1 (17%)	0 (0%)	1 (50%)
Urine blood (Haemolyzed)			
Large	18 (69%)	9 (75%)	9 (64%)
Moderate	5 (19%)	1 (8.3%)	4 (29%)
Small	1 (3.8%)	0 (0%)	1 (7.1%)
Trace	2 (7.7%)	2 (17%)	0 (0%)
Urine protein			
100 ++	6 (19%)	4 (25%)	2 (13%)
30 +	10 (31%)	5 (31%)	5 (31%)
Negative	11 (34%)	5 (31%)	6 (38%)
Trace	5 (16%)	2 (13%)	3 (19%)
Urine leukocytes			
Large +++	1 (3.1%)	1 (6.3%)	0 (0%)
Moderate ++	2 (6.3%)	1 (6.3%)	1 (6.3%)
Negative	20 (63%)	11 (69%)	9 (56%)
Small +	5 (16%)	1 (6.3%)	4 (25%)
Trace	4 (13%)	2 (13%)	2 (13%)
ALT/SGPT (IU/L)	17 (12)	15 (11)	19 (13)
AST/SGOT (IU/L)	135 (126)	140 (133)	130 (122)

Characteristic	Overall, N = 40 ¹	No Paracetamol, N = 20 ¹	Paracetamol, N = 20 ¹
LDH (IU/L)	1,277 (827)	1,325 (888)	1,224 (775)
Total bilirubin (mg/dL)	1.53 (3.04)	1.24 (1.76)	1.84 (4.00)
Conjugated Bilirubin (mmol/L)	10 (33)	4 (6)	16 (48)

Renal recovery at 48 hours

Children in the Paracetamol (1) arm achieved an average renal recovery time of 39.158 hours (95% CI: 32.414 to 45.902) while children in the No Paracetamol Arm (0) achieved an average renal recovery time of 38.667 hours (95% CI: 31.617 to 45.717) within 48 hours (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. The figure illustrates the Kaplan-Meier survival curves for renal recovery over time in the paracetamol group (arm = 1) and the no paracetamol group (arm = 0), with corresponding restricted mean survival time (RMST) estimates for $\tau = 48$ hours

The average time to renal recovery in the Paracetamol Arm was 0.49 hours longer than the No Paracetamol Arm, but this difference was not statistically significant as indicated by RMST difference of 0.491 hours (95% CI: -9.265 to 10.248; $p = 0.921$). The time to renal recovery in the Paracetamol Arm was 1.3% longer than the No Paracetamol Arm, but this ratio was also not statistically significant as indicated by the RMST ratio of 1.013 (95% CI: 0.788 to 1.301; $p = 0.921$) as shown in Table 2.

Table 2
Between-group comparisons for renal recovery at 48 hours.

Paracetamol vs No paracetamol	Estimate	95% Confidence Interval	p-value
Difference in RMST	0.491 hours	(-9.27, 10.25)	0.921
Ratio of RMST (1 / 0)	1.013	(0.788, 1.301)	0.921

After adjusting for Age and weight, the average time to renal recovery in the paracetamol group (arm = 1) was 1.04 hours longer than in the no-paracetamol group (arm = 0), however, this difference was not statistically significant as indicated by the adjusted difference in RMST between the groups of 1.04 hours (95% CI: -8.61, 10.70; $p = 0.832$). The model coefficients further indicated that for each additional year of age, the RMST increased by 3.76 hours (95% CI: -0.93, 8.46; $p = 0.116$), but this was not statistically significant, while for each additional unit increase in weight, the RMST decreases by 1.89 hours (95% CI: -5.17, 1.39; $p = 0.259$), but this was also not statistically significant. The adjusted average recovery time in the paracetamol group was 2.7% higher than in the no-paracetamol group, but this was not statistically significant as indicated by the adjusted RMST ratio between the two groups was 1.027

hours (95% CI: 0.801, 1.317; $p = 0.834$). For each additional year of age, the RMST ratio increases by a factor of 1.098, suggesting older children recover slightly faster, but this was not statistically significant ($p = 0.120$), while for each unit increase in weight, the RMST ratio decreases by a factor of 0.955, suggesting heavier children recover more slowly, but this was also not statistically significant ($p = 0.276$) as shown in the model summary Table 3.

Table 3
Adjusted RMST analysis model summary for renal recovery within 48 hours.

Difference of RMST						
Variable	Coefficient	Standard Error	z-value	p-value	95% CI	
Intercept	48.094	17.256	2.787	0.005	(14.27, 81.92)	
Arm (1 – 0)	1.044	4.925	0.212	0.832	(-8.61, 10.70)	
Age	3.764	2.393	1.573	0.116	(-0.93, 8.46)	
Weight	-1.888	1.674	-1.128	0.259	(-5.17, 1.39)	
Ratio of RMST						
Variable	Coefficient	Standard Error	z-value	p-value	Exp (Coefficient)	95% CI
Intercept	3.874	0.449	8.627	0.000	48.130	(19.96, 116.04)
Arm (1 / 0)	0.027	0.127	0.210	0.834	1.027	(0.801, 1.317)
Age	0.093	0.060	1.553	0.120	1.098	(0.976, 1.235)
Weight	-0.046	0.043	-1.090	0.276	0.955	(0.878, 1.038)

Renal recovery at day 28

Children treated with paracetamol (Arm 1) achieved renal recovery in an average of 279.16 hours (95% CI: 143.57–414.75), while children in the no paracetamol group (Arm 0) achieved recovery in an average of 308.78 hours (95% CI: 161.28–456.28) within 28 days (Fig. 3).

On average, children in the paracetamol arm had a 29.62-hour (95% CI: -229.97 to 170.73; $p = 0.772$) shorter renal recovery time compared to the no paracetamol arm, but this difference was not statistically significant. The recovery time in the paracetamol arm was approximately 90.4% of the recovery time in the no paracetamol arm, but this result was not statistically significant as indicated by the RMST ratio of 0.904 (95% CI: 0.457–1.787; $p = 0.772$) as shown in supplementary table 1. After adjusting for Age and

weight, the average time to renal recovery in the paracetamol group (arm = 1) was 9.1 hours shorter than in the no-paracetamol group (arm = 0), but this difference was not statistically significant as indicated by adjusted RMST between the groups of -9.10 hours (95% CI: -192.23 to 174.02; $p = 0.922$). The model coefficients indicated that for each additional year of age, the RMST decreases by 9.14 hours (95% CI: -93.48, 75.19; $p = 0.832$), but this is not statistically significant, while for each additional unit increase in weight, the RMST increases by 38.82 hours (95% CI: -23.68, 101.32; $p = 0.223$), but this is also not statistically significant. The adjusted average recovery time in the paracetamol group was essentially the same as in the no-paracetamol group, with no significant difference as indicated by the adjusted RMST ratio of 1.003 (95% CI: 0.536 to 1.875; $p = 0.992$). The model coefficients for the covariates indicated that older children tend to recover slightly slower, with an RMST ratio of 0.992 (95% CI: 0.768, 1.280; $p = 0.949$), but this is not statistically significant, while heavier children recover slightly faster, with an RMST ratio of 1.126 (95% CI: 0.945, 1.342; $p = 0.185$), but this is also not statistically significant as shown in supplementary table 2 .

Safety outcomes

There were no significant differences in the observed adverse events and severe adverse events between the paracetamol treated group and control group. Hepatotoxicity was assessed using alanine aminotransferase (ALT), aspartate aminotransferase (AST), lactate dehydrogenase (LDH), and bilirubin levels with no significant differences observed between groups at baseline or 48 hours and changes from baseline. No participants in either group fulfilled the Hy's law criteria for drug-induced hepatotoxicity (Table 4).

Table 4. Safety assessment between the groups

	No Paracetamol (N=20)	Paracetamol (N=20)	Test Statistic
ALT _{0hours}	5.4 10.9 18.9	11.5 17.9 25.9	F _{1,39} =2.29, P=0.14 ³
ALT _{48hours}	3.7 8.0 15.1	5.7 8.3 15.9	F _{1,39} =0.34, P=0.56 ³
Δ ALT _{0-48 hours}	-7.1 -1.8 -0.5	-12.2 -8.8 -2.2	F _{1,39} =2.43, P=0.13 ³
AST _{0hours}	20.7 69.2 243.9	43.0 89.4 229.2	F _{1,39} =0.39, P=0.54 ³
AST _{48hours}	9.3 17.9 38.8	19.3 26.3 34.1	F _{1,39} =0.68, P=0.42 ³
Δ AST _{0-48 hours}	-197.7 -51.9 -9.9	-168.2 -62.5 -26.4	F _{1,39} =0.07, P=0.79 ³
LDH _{0hours}	565.1 876.5 2154.7	714.4 887.6 1520.1	F _{1,39} =0.01, P=0.91 ³
LDH _{48hours}	428.1 604.8 1196.2	529.7 749.1 1045.3	F _{1,39} =0.04, P=0.85 ³
Δ LDH _{0-48 hours}	-686.2 -293.2 4.3	-903.4 -273.8 -75.6	F _{1,39} =0.02, P=0.88 ³
Total bilirubin _{0hours}	2.4 4.3 21.4	2.3 10.3 32.2	F _{1,39} =0.62, P=0.44 ³
Total bilirubin _{48hours}	1.7 1.7 8.1	0.3 1.7 9.7	F _{1,39} =0.03, P=0.86 ³
Δ Total bilirubin _{0-48 hours}	-18.5 -1.7 1.0	-29.9 -3.4 -1.7	F _{1,39} =1.34, P=0.26 ³
Direct bilirubin _{0hours}	0.9 2.1 4.1	0.9 3.4 6.9	F _{1,39} =0.42, P=0.52 ³
Direct bilirubin _{48hours}	0.6 1.0 2.9	0.4 1.6 4.7	F _{1,39} =0.47, P=0.50 ³
Δ Direct bilirubin _{0-48 hours}	-2.5 -0.4 0.2	-2.9 -1.1 -0.1	F _{1,39} =0.42,

	No Paracetamol (N=20)	Paracetamol (N=20)	Test Statistic
			P=0.52 ³
Indirect bilirubin _{0hours}	1.1 3.2 17.3	1.6 5.2 20.0	F _{1,39} =0.42, P=0.52 ³
Indirect bilirubin _{48hours}	-0.2 1.3 5.1	-0.3 1.3 3.6	F _{1,39} =0.01, P=0.91 ³
Δ Indirect bilirubin _{0-48 hours}	-15.1 -1.9 0.1	-20.8 -2.6 -0.5	F _{1,39} =0.47, P=0.50 ³
ALT _{48hrs} >3x ULN + Total bilirubin >2X ULN[1]	0		0
ALT _{48hrs} >3x ULN + Indirect bilirubin ≥2X ULN*		0	0
AST _{48hrs} >3x ULN + Total bilirubin >2X ULN*	0		0
AST _{48hrs} >3x ULN + Indirect bilirubin >2X ULN*	0	0	
Mortality	0.1 2/20	0.0 1/20	χ ² ₁ = 0.36, P=0.55 ²
Vomiting	0.3 7/20	0.2 5/20	χ ² ₁ = 0.48, P=0.49 ²
Right upper quadrant abdominal pain	0.1 3/20	0.2 4/20	χ ² ₁ = 0.17, P=0.68 ²
Allergic rash	0	0	
Diarrhea	0.0 1/20	0.1 2/20	χ ² ₁ = 0.36, P=0.55 ²

¹Kruskal-Wallis ²Pearson ³Wilcoxon.

Data are presented as number (%) or median (IQR), unless otherwise specified as mean (95% CI). Fisher's exact test and Mann-Whitney U test were used to assess differences between categorical and continuous variables. T-tests were employed for comparing differences in log-normal transformed data. The upper limit of normal (ULN) for ALT and AST were 50 U/L and 35 U/L for males and females, respectively. Indirect bilirubin was calculated as total bilirubin minus direct bilirubin.

Abbreviations: ALT, alanine aminotransferase; AST, aspartate aminotransferase; LDH, Lactate Dehydrogenase.

[1] Hy's Law stipulates that: (i) A drug must cause hepatocellular injury, indicated by a 3-fold or greater elevation above the ULN of ALT or AST compared to control or placebo: (ii) In patients with ALT or AST > 3×ULN, there must be an elevation in serum total bilirubin >2×ULN, without evidence of cholestasis; (iii) No other explanation accounts for the combination of elevated ALT/AST and bilirubin levels.

Discussion

This study evaluated the treatment feasibility, safety and preliminary effectiveness of paracetamol as a renoprotective adjunctive treatment for malaria-induced AKI in children. Despite promising findings in adult studies indicating paracetamol's potential renoprotective effects, our phase I/II trial found no significant difference in renal recovery at 48 hours and day 28 between the paracetamol-treated group compared to the control group.

This contrasts with findings from studies in adult populations with AKI [18–21]. For instance, Plewes et al. (2018) reported that regular paracetamol administration protected kidney function in adult patients with moderate and severe falciparum malaria [21]. While in adult patients with sepsis, paracetamol was associated with a reductions in markers of renal injury, such as serum creatinine, and an improvement in renal function [18–20]. Several factors may explain the discrepancy between our findings: firstly, there is a difference in the pathophysiology of AKI across age groups. In paediatric populations, AKI often has multiple causes, including renal tubular damage, vasoconstriction, and inflammation, which may differ from adult aetiologies [27]. Additionally, the therapeutic efficacy and safety profile of paracetamol, may be significantly affected by the maturation of renal function and differences in drug metabolism between children and adults. In children, renal clearance and metabolic pathways are not fully developed, resulting in differing drug pharmacokinetics. For instance, the glucuronidation capacity, essential for paracetamol metabolism, matures over time, affecting drug clearance rates in neonates and infants [28]. Moreover, drug absorption, distribution, metabolism, and excretion may be affected by age-related physiological differences, such as gastric pH, intestinal transit time, and enzyme activity [29].

Notably, our findings suggest that targeting oxidative stress alone with paracetamol may be insufficient to address the complex pathogenesis of malaria-induced AKI in children. This pathogenesis is multifactorial, involving hemodynamic disturbances, immune-mediated damage, and metabolic dysregulation [30, 31]. For example, the cytoadherence of parasitized red blood cells to the microvascular endothelium leads to impaired renal perfusion and ischemic injury [32], a mechanism that is distinct from oxidative stress alone. In addition, immune-mediated injury through excessive release of cytokines, including TNF- α and IL-6, contributes to inflammation and endothelial dysfunction, which further exacerbates the renal injury [33, 34]. While the role of oxidative stress in malaria-induced AKI is significant, its is interlinked with these broader mechanisms. For example, cell-free haemoglobin released during hemolysis contributes to oxidative stress [35] but also interacts with nitric oxide

pathways, impairing vasodilation and exacerbating renal hypoperfusion [36]. Moreover, the metabolic derangements including, lactic acidosis and disrupted renal autoregulation, further complicate the clinical course [37]. These observations underscore the complexity of the underlying mechanisms in malaria-induced AKI in children and demonstrate that therapeutic interventions targeting a single pathway may fail to achieve substantial benefits of renal recovery in this group. Regarding safety, our findings did not show significant liver injury associated with paracetamol use, implying that short-term administration is safe in this context. However, caution is warranted with higher doses or prolonged use, as paracetamol has been associated with nephrotoxicity [38]. Additionally, nephrotoxicity following paracetamol ingestion can occur even in the absence of hepatotoxicity, emphasizing the need for careful dosing [39, 40].

A notable strength of this study is that it had a well-characterized cohort with rigorous follow-up. In addition, the application of RMST analysis, provided a robust and interpretable estimate of treatment effect over time. However, given that phase I/II trials are designed to explore treatment feasibility and assess safety, it is important to recognise that these findings are exploratory. The study was not powered to detect small difference in efficacy and the small sample size of 40 participants may limit generalisability of the findings.

Therefore, while paracetamol did not show a significant renoprotective effect in this trial, it is possible that larger, multicentre phase III trials with more diverse populations and stratification by severity of oxidative stress may identify which subgroups benefit from this paracetamol effect. Further studies should also investigate therapies that target the multifactorial mechanisms involved in malaria-induced AKI.

Conclusion

This study found that paracetamol was safe and well tolerated with no significant adverse events or hepatotoxicity, however, no significant improvement in renal recovery was observed between the paracetamol-treated group compared with the control group. The lack of preliminary efficacy observed in this trial does not preclude a potential renoprotective role of paracetamol in malaria-induced AKI, given the exploratory nature of the study design and the small sample size limitation. Further large-scale studies involving diverse populations are needed to establish the definitive efficacy and identify subgroups that may benefit from this paracetamol effect.

Abbreviations

AKI	Acute Kidney Injury
ALT	Alanine Aminotransferase
AST	Aspartate Aminotransferase
BUN	Blood Urea Nitrogen
CI	Confidence Interval
CFHb	Cell-Free Haemoglobin
CRF	Case Report Form
CTCAE	Common Terminology Criteria for Adverse Events
DSMB	Data Safety Monitoring Board
Hb	Hemoglobin
iSTAT®	Point-of-Care Blood Analyzer (brand name)
ISRCTN	International Standard Randomised Controlled Trial Number
KPI	Kampala Pharmaceutical Industries
LDH	Lactate Dehydrogenase
MCRI	Mbale Clinical Research Institute
MRRH	Mbale Regional Referral Hospital
<i>P. falciparum</i>	<i>Plasmodium falciparum</i>
RMST	Restricted Mean Survival Time
RCT	Randomised Controlled Trial
SSA	Sub-Saharan Africa
ULN	Upper Limit of Normal

Declarations

Ethical approval and consent to participate

Ethical approval before starting this trial was granted by the Mbale Regional Referral Hospital Research Ethics Committee (MRRH-REC OUT 002/2019) while, regulatory approval was granted from the Uganda National Council of Science and Technology (UNCST) (HS965ES) and the National Drug Authority (NDA) (CTC 0166/2021). Written informed consent was obtained from the parents or guardians of all participating children, ensuring full compliance with ethical guidelines for research involving human subjects.

Consent for publication

This work has been approved for publication by the Mbale Clinical Research Institute.

Availability of data and materials

The data supporting the results of this study will be made available upon reasonable request. Deidentified individual level data, including clinical outcomes, laboratory results and treatment information, will be shared along with the data dictionary. These data will be accessible three months from publication of manuscript and will be available for the period of five years following the publication. The data will be hosted on Mendeley Data, where a permanent and unique digital image identifier (DOI) will be assigned for easy referencing. The specific URL and DOI for accessing the data will be provided three months after the publication. Access to the data will be granted to qualified researchers for non-commercial academic purposes. To obtain the data, researchers must submit a data access proposal detailing the type of analysis to be performed. Access will only be granted following approval of the proposal, and a signed data access agreement will be required before the data are released.

Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing of interests.

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Author contributions

All authors have made substantive intellectual contributions to the development of this manuscript. PO-O conceptualised the clinical trial and provided general guidance to the research team. All authors are involved in the implementation of this trial. GA and CN designed the database. PO, WO, DA, CN and MO are involved in data collection. RM and GM initially developed the laboratory analytical plan and schedule and did the laboratory tests. CBO oversaw the investigational product handling and storage. GP and CN did the statistical analysis, GP initiated the first draft of the manuscript, which was then followed by numerous iterations with substantial input and appraisal from all the authors. All authors approved the final version of the manuscript.

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Figures

Figure 1

CONSORT diagram, illustrating the screening, randomization, and follow-up processes

Figure 2

The figure illustrates the Kaplan-Meier survival curves for renal recovery over time in the paracetamol group (arm = 1) and the no paracetamol group (arm = 0), with corresponding restricted mean survival time (RMST) estimates for $\tau=48$ hours

Figure 3

The figure illustrates the Kaplan-Meier survival curves for renal recovery over time in the paracetamol group (arm = 1) and the no paracetamol group (arm = 0), with corresponding restricted mean survival time (RMST) estimates for $\tau=672$ hour (day 28)

Supplementary Files

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